

ALTERNATIVE RECONSTRUCTION AND ACQUISITION TECHNIQUES FOR IMAGING LARGE CFRP SAMPLES

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ABSTRACT

X-ray Computed Tomography (CT) is a powerful tool for non-destructive imaging of materials but is ill-suited for scanning the high aspect ratio geometries typical of standard test pieces and industrial composite panels. Computed Laminography (CL) offers a solution to overcome the current limitations of CT by using a tilted axis of rotation. This work demonstrates how a CL trajectory may be implemented on a conventional laboratory-based CT system with source and detector offsets. The performance of the technique was compared to a standard CT scan for region-of-interest imaging of a large carbon-fibre laminate plate. A low tilt angle of 20° was found to produce superior image quality to CT in slices through the face of the sample whilst mitigating the associated laminographic artefacts across horizontal views. The resulting fibre orientation analysis demonstrated CL to be an effective technique to accurately characterise the fibre architecture of large composite structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

X-ray computed tomography (CT) is becoming an increasingly important non-destructive imaging technique for the internal microstructural characterisation of fibre-reinforced polymers, both during manufacturing and under in-service conditions [1]. Despite recent advancements in the capabilities of laboratory-based CT systems, the constituent material properties of carbon-fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP) coupled with the typically high aspect ratio geometries of industrial components provide fundamental challenges to high-resolution X-ray imaging. One of the main concerns for CFRP and an important factor for feature detection is image contrast. The small difference in attenuation coefficient results in low contrast between the fibres and polymer resin within the greyscale image, for which a low tube voltage is likely required but at the expense of penetration depth through the sample [2]. Consequently making it more difficult to distinguish fibres for orientation analysis and/or defects such as narrow matrix cracks. Also, with individual fibre diameters between 5-7µm, the physical dimensions of real industrial components often impede on the geometric magnification necessary to resolve small bundles or strands giving a trade-off between sample size and spatial resolution. Further, flat plate-like geometries characteristic of industrial composite panels and specific standard test pieces are ill-suited conventional CT imaging. The high aspect ratio means that X-ray energies which optimise the dynamic range face-on are likely insufficient for imaging the plate edge-on. As such, the large difference in absorption through different projection angles result in pronounced reconstruction artefacts [3]. For region-of-interest (ROI) scanning of flat plate carbon-fibre sheet moulded compound, this constitutes sample sizes greater than 75% excess material experiencing a significant decline of in image quality [4].

A potential solution to overcome these challenges is computed laminography (CL). Rotary CL is the simplest trajectory, and like CT it consists of the acquisition of projection datasets, but the axis of rotation is inclined by an angle (<90°) instead of being perpendicular to the X-ray beam [5]. By tilting the axis of rotation planar samples can be positioned closer to the X-ray source and achieve a similar x-ray transmission through all projection angles to provide improvements in noise level and resolution. This technique has been successfully implemented using synchrotron radiation to provide

high-resolution, in-situ, three-dimensional analysis of structure failure in polymer composites, otherwise unattainable via CT [6]. It is possible to implement CL trajectories using commercial laboratory X-ray CT systems; however, its application so far has been dependant on sample manipulator arms which are not readily available at most facilities [7,8]. Although CL provides an efficient method to image flat samples its reconstruction is an ill-posed problem. Due to the tilted scanning trajectory, sampling of the object in the Fourier domain is incomplete, therefore, CL reconstruction inherently suffers from tail artefacts and inter-slice aliasing. The severity of which is proportional to the extent of laminographic tilt angle. Traditionally, this angle has been fixed to either 30° or 45° to reduce the X-ray path length through sufficiently dense samples such as printed circuit boards. Hence, it can be inferred that better quality laminography results are obtained with lower tilt angles ($\leq 30^\circ$) and for more homogeneous samples [9]. It has been shown that suppression of laminography artefacts can be achieved using iterative reconstruction with total variation (TV) regularization [9,10] but this involves careful selection of the regularization parameter. A commonly observed drawback of TV-regularisation is the loss of fine details, as such, it is often advisable to search for a balance between artefact suppression and over-smoothing especially in cases that include important small features such as polymer composites.

This paper demonstrates how a CL trajectory can be accomplished using a conventional laboratory CT system, without the need for specialist equipment, through source and detector offsets. The performance of the method is compared to a standard CT scan for a large CFRP plate and is assessed in terms of image quality and its application for fibre orientation analysis. As this trajectory limits the maximum laminographic tilt angle, the achievable image quality for a low tilt angle across both vertical and side views are evaluated to explore if iterative reconstruction methods are necessary to perform characterization tasks for polymer composites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGIES

2.1 Composite specimen

In this work, the composite material studied is a quasi-isotropic CFRP plate, as shown in Figure 1, obtained from Easy Composite (product code: CFS-RI-1-0056) with dimensions $250\text{ mm} \times 230\text{ mm} \times 4\text{ mm}$. The layup schedule for the specimen consists of eight layers arranged symmetrically as follows: 210g 2/2 twill, 300g $\pm 45^\circ$ biaxial, four consecutive layers of 650g 2/2 twill, 300g $\pm 45^\circ$ biaxial, and 210g 2/2 twill layer.

2.2 CL Trajectory

The acquisition process is similar for both imaging techniques with projections obtained as the object rotates 360° around the rotation axis. For CL, the source and detector are positioned to different heights on opposite sides of the object stage. Specifically, the source is lowered, and the detector is raised to tilt the optical axis of the CT system and achieve a rotary CL trajectory (Figure 2). The extent of vertical translation for the detector permits a maximum laminographic tilt angle of 20° which was used in this study. A key benefit of this CL trajectory appears at magnifications corresponding to a $\geq 15\mu\text{m}$ voxel size, where the displacement is sufficient for larger samples to rotate freely above the source without risk of collision to enable higher resolutions otherwise unattainable with CT.

2.3 X-ray Acquisition

Both scan trajectories were performed on the TESCAN UniTom XL (TESCAN, Czech Republic) XCT system using a detector cropped to 2000-pixel square, 2005mm from the source, which with magnification of the sample, resulted in a $14\mu\text{m}$ voxel size. For fair comparison, the acquisition parameters remained constant between the CT and CL scans with the exception of exposure time. A voltage of 40kV was used to provide adequate penetration and contrast for both trajectories. The power was selected such that the spot size was approximately equal to pixel size, and exposure chosen

to maximise the dynamic range as described in the standardised setup process [2]. To minimise the X-ray path length for each scan the sample was mounted vertically in CT and horizontally in CL. Using the CT trajectory projections viewing the flat plate edge-on experienced propagation-based phase effects causing over-saturation, therefore, resulting in the difference between exposure times of 2.4s and 3.5s for CT and CL, respectively. A total of 3000 projections were collected using step-and-shoot mode and three averages. Both datasets were then reconstructed using the Feldkamp, Davis, and Kress (FDK) algorithm within Panthera.

Figure 1: Flat plate geometry with 250mm width and 4mm thickness. The red box indicated the 28mm field-of-view achieved at 14 μ m voxel size.

Figure 2: Schematic representation illustrating the CL acquisition geometry.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The centre slice reconstructions are displayed in Figures 3 and 4 for CT and CL, respectively. Visually, the CT reconstruction does provide adequate image quality to observe the fibre architecture; however, the high aspect ratio geometry of the specimen contributed to several artefacts across each view. The view through the face of the specimen (3a) contains a pronounced ring artefact, characteristic of anisotropic attenuation, and due to its appearance it can obscure small defects and/or be mistaken for fibres during computational analysis. Additionally, horizontal fibres orientated parallel to the axis of rotation encounter a noticeable drop in sharpness. With CT, this issue presents another trade-off for flat plate laminates with $0^\circ/90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$ ply orientations since any alternative positioning of the specimen to avoid this would further increase x-ray path lengths. When observing the plate edge-on (3b), the extent of image noise across the volume makes it difficult to distinguish the lay-up scheme or identify any defects. Alternatively, the CL reconstruction (Figure 4) produces superior image quality in terms of noise and suppression of attenuation-based artefacts especially in views through the thickness of the specimen. As shown in (4a), the ring artefact is effectively removed and fibres appear brighter, owing to the increased x-ray exposure time, and maintain sharpness of the fibre bundles in both the vertical and horizontal direction. In addition, the reduction of noise due to consistent absorption through projection angles can be quantified by CL having nearly double the signal-to-noise (SNR) ratio to that of CT with SNR values of 11.82 and 5.99, accordingly. It can therefore be inferred that thicker composites are likely to experience greater improvements in image quality from CL as they exhibit a higher proportion of projection angles associated with longer X-ray path lengths in CT. Due to the relatively low 20° tilt angle, the horizontal view (4b) does not extensively suffer from laminography artefacts which in this case consist of a cone beam artefact above the specimen proportional to the tilt angle and a slight inter-slice aliasing for plies orientated in the x-direction. With the significant reduction in noise and retention of spatial resolution of horizontal plies, the side view through CL is preferable to CT for visual observation of the specimen's lay-up scheme.

To evaluate the task-based effectiveness of each imaging technique fibre orientation analysis was performed for each volume using VGSTUDIO MAX 2024.1. The corresponding space orientation for each slice is shown in Figures 3(c-e) for CT and Figure 4(c-e) for CL. As illustrated in Figures 3(c) and 4(c), the analyses well replicate the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ weave pattern through the specimen's thickness and well match what can be observed from image slice. In both cases, some individual voxels within a bundle are subject to misorientation of 45° despite the improvement in image noise for CL. Since the investigation is on fibre bundles the small fluctuations can be resolved by increasing the integration area radius to up to half the bundle height, as shown in Figures 3(e) and 4(e) for the perpendicular view when this parameter is set to two voxels. The main difference between analyses of the weave fibre slices lies with the ring artefact in the CT reconstruction being incorrectly identified as horizontal fibres as seen by the blue strip through the centre of the image (3c). For side views facing the plate edge-on, the outer unidirectional and horizontal weave plies are more faithfully represented with CL (4d) than CT (3d) due to the significant decrease in image noise along this plane. The consequence of the slight inter-slice aliasing artefacts in CL is demonstrated within low depth areas of weave fibres orientated in the horizontal-x direction where voxels are misoriented to 45° . Although, increasing the area parameter to two voxels (4e) produces a more accurate portrayal of vertical fibres that reflect the results of CT (3d&e). Since for practical applications this parameter is optimised in accordance with the specimen's bundle size, the CL trajectory can be deemed an effective imaging technique to accurately characterise the fibre architecture of high aspect ratio structures. A 20° tilt angle effectively mitigated the expected tail artefacts associated with CL reconstruction using the normative FDK algorithm, as such, TV regularisation methods are likely unnecessary for fibre-based tasks at low laminography tilt angles. However, laboratory-based CL imaging of low-density materials may benefit from standard iterative reconstruction methods to aid high-throughput acquisition whereby the increased scan duration attained by additional exposure time could be offset by reducing the number of projections collected.

3 mm

(3a)

3 mm

(3b)

Figure 3: (a) Central CT slice through the face of the specimen; (b) Central CT slice through the edge of the specimen; (c) Space Orientation of the CT slice presented in (a); (d) Space Orientation of the CT slice presented in (b); (e) Space orientation with an integration area radius of 2.

3 mm

(4a)

3 mm

(4b)

Figure 4: (a) Central CL slice through the face of the specimen; (b) Central CL slice through the edge of the specimen; (c) Space Orientation of the CL slice presented in (a); (d) Space Orientation of the CL slice presented in (b); (e) Space orientation with an integration area radius of 2.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, an alternative laminography trajectory was implemented to characterise the fibre architecture of a large high-aspect ratio carbon-fibre laminate. The CL reconstruction was found to produce superior image quality in the plane parallel to the plate's face compared to CT as quantified by an improvement in SNR of 11.89 from 5.99 for the central slice. CL also avoids the consequences of anisotropic attenuation as shown by the suppression of artefacts and preservation of image sharpness for horizontally aligned fibres. Notably, the main difference in computational analysis between the parallel slices was the pronounced ring artefact in the CT reconstruction being misidentified as horizontal fibres. In the side view, a low tilt angle of 20° alleviates the characteristic laminographic artefacts, at which, standard FDK reconstruction is sufficient for CL reconstruction when imaging composite materials. In fact, due to the significant reduction in image noise in this plane, CL provides more visual information of the specimen's lay-up scheme. Further, the results of orientation analysis demonstrate CL as an effective technique for the accurate calculation of fibre direction in laterally extended samples. Overall, the implementation of the CL trajectory is likely to facilitate the greatest benefit for thicker composites and/or structures larger than 400mm where the specimen is free to rotate over the source to achieve a higher resolution otherwise unattainable with CT. Future work will focus on the application of standard iterative reconstruction methods to CL to reduce acquisition times and facilitate high-throughput inspection.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Garcea, S. C., Wang, Y., & Withers, P. J. (2018). X-ray computed tomography of polymer composites. *Composites Science and Technology*, 156, 305-319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2017.10.023>
- [2] Zwanenburg, E. A., Williams, M. A., & Warnett, J. M. (2022). Review of high-speed imaging with lab-based x-ray computed tomography. *Measurement Science and Technology*, 33(1), 012003. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6501/ac354a>
- [3] Titarenko, S., Titarenko, V., Kyrieleis, A., Withers, P. J., & De Carlo, F. (2011). Suppression of ring artefacts when tomographing anisotropically attenuating samples. *J Synchrotron Radiat*, 18(Pt 3), 427-435. <https://doi.org/10.1107/s0909049511006005>
- [4] Zwanenburg, E. A., Norman, D. G., Qian, C., Kendall, K. N., Williams, M. A., & Warnett, J. M. (2023). Effective X-ray micro computed tomography imaging of carbon fibre composites. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 258, 110707. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2023.110707>
- [5] Helfen, L., Myagotin, A., Mikulík, P., Pernot, P., Voropaev, A., Elyyan, M., Di Michiel, M., Baruchel, J., & Baumbach, T. (2011). On the implementation of computed laminography using synchrotron radiation. *Rev Sci Instrum*, 82(6), 063702. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3596566>
- [6] Xu, F., Helfen, L., Moffat, A. J., Johnson, G., Sinclair, I., & Baumbach, T. (2010). Synchrotron radiation computed laminography for polymer composite failure studies. *J Synchrotron Radiat*, 17(2), 222-226. <https://doi.org/10.1107/s0909049510001512>
- [7] Wood, C. E., O'Brien, N., Denysov, A., & Blumensath, T. (2019). Computed Laminography of CFRP Using an X-Ray Cone-Beam and Robotic Sample Manipulator Systems. *IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science*, 66(3), 655-663. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TNS.2019.2895910>
- [8] Fisher, S. L., Holmes, D. J., Jørgensen, J. S., Gajjar, P., Behnsen, J., Lionheart, W. R. B., & Withers, P. J. (2019). Laminography in the lab: imaging planar objects using a conventional x-ray CT

scanner. *Measurement Science and Technology*, 30(3), 035401. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6501/aafcae>

[9] Jørgensen, J. S., Ametova, E., Burca, G., Fardell, G., Papoutsellis, E., Pasca, E., Thielemans, K., Turner, M., Warr, R., Lionheart, W. R. B., & Withers, P. J. (2021). Core Imaging Library - Part I: a versatile Python framework for tomographic imaging. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A Mathematical Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 379(2204), 20200192.

<https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2020.0192>

[10] Nikitin, V., Wildenberg, G., Mittone, A., Shevchenko, P., Deriy, A., & De Carlo, F. (2024). Laminography as a tool for imaging large-size samples with high resolution. *J Synchrotron Radiat*, 31(Pt 4), 851-866. <https://doi.org/10.1107/s1600577524002923>